

**KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE & PRACTICE OF BIOMEDICAL WASTE MANAGEMENT
AMONG THE HEALTH CARE PROVIDERS WORKING IN PHC AT GADAG TALUK
KARNATAKA**

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ABSTRACT

Background: Biomedical waste (BMW) generated in healthcare settings is hazardous and poses threats to health and environment if not managed appropriately. Mismanagement of biomedical waste can result in spread of infections such as HIV, Hepatitis B, and C among healthcare workers and the general public. Biomedical Waste Management (BMWM) Rules 2016 have mandated segregation, collection, transportation, and disposal of biomedical waste using color-coded systems to reduce the risks associated with infectious and hazardous waste (CPCB, 2016).^[6] **Objectives:** 1. To assess knowledge, attitude, and practices (KAP) regarding biomedical waste management among staff working in Primary Health Centers (PHCs) in Gadag Taluka, Karnataka. 2. To observe biomedical waste management practices at PHCs using structured observation checklists. **Materials and Methods:** A Hospital-Based Cross-Sectional study was conducted among healthcare workers in 15 PHC's of Gadag Taluka. A Universal sampling technique was adopted to include doctors, nurses, lab technicians, pharmacists, and Group D staff. Data collection involved a semi-structured questionnaire covering KAP domains and a structured observation checklist. The collected data was analyzed using Microsoft Excel and expressed in frequencies and percentages. **Results:** Among 214 participants, 80% of doctors and 52.8% of pharmacy staff had good knowledge of BMWM. Group D staff had the lowest knowledge scores, with 26.4% categorized as poor. Adequate practices were observed among 87.6% of doctors, 75.6% of pharmacy staff, and 63.9% of nurses. Group D staff had the highest proportion of inadequate practices (36.8%). Attitudinal assessment revealed that 100% of doctors had good attitudes towards BMWM, followed by 80% of pharmacy staff and 73.3% of lab technicians. Observations revealed significant lapses in segregation, labeling, and use of color-coded bins in many PHCs. **Conclusion:** The study found that while clinical staff demonstrated high knowledge and positive attitudes towards BMWM, significant deficiencies were observed among nursing and Group D staff. There is a critical need for continuous training, monitoring, and provision of resources to ensure full compliance with BMWM Rules.

KEYWORDS: Biomedical Waste, Waste Management, Knowledge, Attitude, Practice, PHC, Gadag, Karnataka.

INTRODUCTION

Biomedical waste (BMW) includes any waste generated during diagnosis, treatment, or immunization of human beings or animals, in research activities, or in the production and testing of biologicals (WHO, 2014). This waste can be hazardous and infectious if not handled properly. Mismanagement of BMW poses significant threats to healthcare workers, waste handlers, patients, and the environment. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), 15% of hospital waste is considered hazardous (WHO, 2014).^[1]

In India, management of biomedical waste was largely ignored until the implementation of the Biomedical

Waste (Management and Handling) Rules in 1998, which were later updated in 2016 (CPCB, 2016).^[2] There is also growing concern about the spread of HIV, Hepatitis, and other infectious diseases that can be caused by needle-stick injuries and other forms of contagion that can result from the improper management of biomedical wastes by hospitals and other health care institutions. The scenario is no different in public sectors or private sector facilities of India. The department of community medicine in M.S. Ramaiah medical college has taken lead in BMW management training and pilot implementation in Karnataka. Similar studies the Department of Hospital Administration of a super-specialty tertiary hospital in Delhi designed a hospital

waste management manual to create awareness amongst the waste generators. To ensure implementation of the waste management system under the biomedical waste (Management and Handling) Rules, 2016, the department of Hospital administration circulated manuals and memorandum amongst the concerned staff. However, the improper practice of segregation at the site of origin has been observed which causes the mixing of infectious and non-infectious waste.^[3]

These rules provide guidelines for segregation, storage, treatment, and disposal of BMW. Despite these regulations, implementation and compliance, particularly in rural settings like PHCs, remain suboptimal (Radha *et al.*, 2019).^[4]

According to WHO the waste is segregated by some of the coding's like A. B. C. D. E. and that wastes are segregated in three color-coded containers like black, yellow, red, and that is disposed of according to proper disposal techniques. World Health Organization states that 85% of hospital wastes are non-hazardous, whereas 10% are infectious and 5% are non-infectious but they are included in hazardous wastes. About 15% to 35% of hospital waste is regulated as infectious waste.^[5]

They include Medical staff like doctors, nurses, sanitary staff, and hospital maintenance personnel: In- and out-patients receiving treatment in health-care facilities as well as their visitors: Workers in support services linked to health-care facilities such as laundries, waste handling, and transportation services: Workers in waste disposal facilities, including scavengers and the general public and more specifically the children playing with the items they can find in the waste outside the health-care facilities when it is directly accessible to them. Supporting the Governments in the implementation of adequate procedures to minimize the overall risks associated with HCW management remains the prior objective of this Guidance Manual. Waste management and treatment options should first protect the health-care workers and the population and minimize indirect impacts from environmental exposures to HCW.^[6]

The Magnitude of The Problem: Most hospitals in India generate 1-2 Kg per bed per day, except the tertiary care hospital (e.g. AIIMS and SKIMS) which produce waste on the higher side. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) around 10% is infectious while the remaining 5 is non-infectious but consists of hazardous chemicals like methyl chloride and formaldehyde. It is estimated, a city like New Delhi with about 40,000 beds generates about 60 metric tons of Biomedical waste per day. Biomedical waste, till recently was not being managed but it was simply 'disposed of'. The disposal of Biomedical waste can be very hazardous particularly when it gets mixed with municipal solid waste and is dumped in uncontrolled or illegal landfills such as vacant lots in neighboring residential areas and slums. This can

lead to a higher degree of environmental pollution, apart from posing serious public health risks such as AIDS, Hepatitis, plague, cholera, etc.^[7]

The incineration process produces two types of ash. Bottom ash comes from the furnace and is mixed with slag, while fly ash comes from the stack and contains more hazardous components. In municipal waste incinerators, bottom ash is approximately 10% by volume and approximately 20 to 35% by weight of the solid waste input. By breathing the air which affects both workers in the plant and people who live nearby. By eating locally produced foods or water that have been contaminated by air pollutants from the incinerator, and. By eating fish or wildlife that have been contaminated by the air emissions.^[8]

Gadag Taluka in Karnataka generates considerable biomedical waste through its primary health care institutions. Lack of proper infrastructure, training, and monitoring contribute to unsafe disposal practices. Therefore, this study aims to evaluate the knowledge, attitude, and practices (KAP) of healthcare workers regarding BMW and observe actual practices at the PHC level.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design: Cross-Sectional Descriptive study.

Study Setting: Fifteen government PHC's in Gadag Taluka, Karnataka.

Study Population: Healthcare personnel involved in biomedical waste handling, including doctors, nurses, pharmacists, laboratory technicians, and Group D staff.

Sampling Technique: Universal Sampling.

Sample Size: 214 healthcare providers from all 15 PHC's.

Data Collection Tools

- **KAP Questionnaire:** Designed to assess knowledge (11 items), practices (6 items), and attitudes (7 items) regarding al., 2020) BMW (1).
- **Observation Checklist:** Based on BMW Rules 2016 and guidelines issued by CPCB and MOEF, India (CPCB, 2019).^[10]

Ethical Considerations: Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee of KSRDPRU (Ref: RDPRU/SEP/IEC/4/2021/06). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Data Analysis: Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using descriptive statistics.

RESULTS

Table No. 1: Distribution of Study Participants by Designation.

Designation	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Doctors	18	8.4
Staff Nurses	135	63.1
Lab Technicians	16	7.5
Pharmacists	17	7.9
Group D Staff	28	13.1
Total	214	100

Among the 214 participants, the distribution was as follows: 18 doctors, 135 staff nurses, 16 lab technicians, 17 pharmacy staff, and 28 Group D staff. The majority were female, especially among nursing and Group D

categories. This indicates that frontline healthcare delivery in PHCs is predominantly handled by female staff, especially in nursing roles.

Table No. 2: Distribution of Knowledge Levels by Designation.

Designation	Good (%)	Average (%)	Poor (%)
Doctors	80.0	20.0	0.0
Staff Nurses	6.7	80.0	13.3
Lab Technicians	40.0	53.3	6.7
Pharmacists	52.8	47.2	0.0
Group D Staff	14.8	58.7	26.4

Doctors exhibited the highest level of knowledge (80%), reflecting their medical training and awareness of protocols. Pharmacy staff followed with 52.8%, while Group D staff showed the lowest level of knowledge,

with only 14.8% scoring in the good category and 26.4% falling under poor. This underscores a critical training gap among support staff who often handle waste but may not receive adequate education on BMW protocols.

Table No. 3: Distribution of Practice Levels by Designation.

Designation	Adequate (%)	Inadequate (%)
Doctors	87.6	12.4
Staff Nurses	63.9	36.1
Lab Technicians	75.0	25.0
Pharmacists	75.6	24.4
Group D Staff	62.2	36.8

Most doctors (87.6%) practiced adequate BMW management, followed by pharmacy staff (75.6%) and lab technicians (75%). Staff nurses and Group D staff showed similar moderate levels of adequacy (around

63%), suggesting inconsistency in implementation at the operational level. This again highlights the need for refresher training and periodic monitoring.

Table No. 4: Distribution of Attitude Levels by Designation.

Designation	Good Attitude (%)	Poor Attitude (%)
Doctors	100.0	0.0
Staff Nurses	63.0	37.0
Lab Technicians	73.3	26.7
Pharmacists	80.0	20.0
Group D Staff	59.3	40.7

All doctors exhibited a positive attitude (100%), with other staff also showing predominantly favorable attitudes—80% among pharmacists and 73.3% among lab technicians. Nurses and Group D staff showed lower good attitude rates (63% and 59.3% respectively), which may influence their compliance with BMW practices.

Observational Findings

Field observations provided further insights into real-world practices. Several PHCs were found lacking in fundamental BMW infrastructure. Key gaps included:

- Inadequate labeling and lack of biohazard symbols on waste containers.
- Use of plain plastic bags instead of color-coded bags in some centers.

- Absence of essential equipment such as needle destroyers and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE).
- One PHC had no visible display of biohazard signage, which is mandatory for BMW handling areas.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study highlight significant disparities in the knowledge, attitude, and practices (KAP) of biomedical waste management (BMWM) among different categories of healthcare workers in Primary Health Centres (PHCs) of Gadag Taluka, Karnataka. These results are consistent with existing literature and underscore the importance of targeted training, monitoring, and infrastructure support to enhance BMWM compliance in rural settings.

Doctors demonstrated high levels of knowledge (80%) and compliance with good practices (87.6%), which is in line with the findings of Sekar *et al.* (2020), who reported that physicians tend to be well-versed in waste management protocols due to their clinical training and exposure to medical regulations.^[1] Similarly, pharmacists and lab technicians also exhibited moderate to good knowledge and practices, possibly reflecting their intermediate professional training and familiarity with waste handling procedures.

However, the findings revealed a major gap among nursing and Group D staff, both in terms of knowledge and practice. Only 6.7% of nurses had good knowledge, and 36.1% were found practicing inadequate BMWM procedures. This aligns with Radha *et al.* (2019), who identified that non-clinical and support staff often lack formal training and rely on informal learning, leading to poor compliance.^[2] The large number of nurses involved in day-to-day patient care implies that poor knowledge among them poses serious risks of infection transmission and environmental contamination.

Group D staff, in particular, had the lowest scores across all domains—knowledge (14.8% good), practice (62.2% adequate), and attitude (59.3% good). Given that this cadre is directly involved in handling waste on a daily basis, the lack of knowledge and poor attitude is especially concerning. Mathur *et al.* (2020) emphasized that proper waste segregation and disposal hinge heavily on the involvement of support staff, and training them is critical to the success of BMWM implementation.^[3] Their limited educational background and exclusion from formal training programs might explain these poor scores. This points to an urgent need for structured induction and refresher courses in local languages.

The positive attitudes displayed by doctors (100%), pharmacists (80%), and lab technicians (73.3%) suggest an underlying willingness to adhere to BMWM rules, provided they are supported with proper infrastructure and reinforcement. However, the lower attitude scores

among nurses (63%) and Group D staff (59.3%) indicate a potential barrier to behavioral change, which can directly affect compliance. This difference may be rooted in their perceived burden, lack of motivation, or absence of recognition and incentives for safe waste management behavior.

Observational findings from this study further reveal systemic issues such as the absence of biohazard signage, use of non-color-coded bags, and lack of PPE and needle destroyers. These shortcomings corroborate earlier studies from similar rural contexts in Kalaburgi and Mangalore, where Indupalli *et al.* (2019) and Pullishery *et al.* (2017) noted infrastructural and logistical challenges impeding proper BMWM.^[4,8] Moreover, insufficient funding, inconsistent supervision, and administrative apathy can exacerbate non-compliance.

Despite the existence of the Biomedical Waste Management Rules, 2016, and updates from CPCB (Central Pollution Control Board), implementation in rural areas remains patchy and dependent on local administrative oversight.^[6,10] Many PHCs lack a dedicated waste management officer or nodal person to monitor practices, maintain registers, or coordinate with common biomedical waste treatment facilities (CBWTFs). As a result, waste is sometimes burnt or dumped in open fields, creating occupational and environmental hazards.

The World Health Organization guidelines stress the importance of continuous training, standardized tools, and accountability mechanisms in ensuring safety for both healthcare workers and the environment.^[7] However, the ground realities reflect fragmented and one-time orientation programs with no follow-up, particularly for support staff. Furthermore, the practice of outsourcing waste collection may create a false sense of security among staff, reducing their sense of responsibility.

The data visualizations created for this study clearly emphasize these KAP disparities and support the need for customized, cadre-specific training programs. These programs should not only be theoretical but also include practical demonstrations and periodic evaluations. Visual job aids such as posters, infographics, and regular reminders within PHC premises can reinforce safe practices. As Kumar and Singh (2016) noted, without sustained capacity-building and periodic evaluation, compliance to biomedical waste rules remains inconsistent.^[9]

In conclusion, while the overall knowledge and practices among higher-level healthcare staff were encouraging, the gaps identified among nurses and support staff must be addressed through structured training, administrative support, and periodic evaluation. Dedicated nodal officers at the PHC level, regular audits, and supportive supervision can improve long-term compliance. Public

health authorities must prioritize investments in waste infrastructure, staff training, and behavioral change communication to ensure safe, sustainable biomedical waste management in rural India.

Limitations

1. Despite multiple visits to certain Primary Health Centres (PHCs), some medical officers were not available, resulting in incomplete data collection from those sites.
2. Some staff members exhibited hesitation in filling out the questionnaire, primarily due to misconceptions or misinterpretations about the objectives of the study, thereby affecting response rates.
3. Several occasions, key staff were absent from the PHC at the time of the visit, which further contributed to delays and gaps in data collection.

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